
THE C-SECTION SURGE: A STRUCTURED LITERATURE REVIEW OF
GLOBAL TRENDS AND LOCAL PERCEPTIONS IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Significant public health concerns have been raised by the global increase in Caesarean section (C-section) deliveries since the 1990s, especially in Pakistan, where rates have risen to over 22%. Although surgical intervention is primarily motivated by medical necessity, there is an increasing need to comprehend how maternal attitudes and socioeconomic factors impact these trends. The purpose of this study was to evaluate C-section delivery trends and look into women's attitudes, views, and level of knowledge about the technique. A descriptive study of women visiting Railway Hospital's outpatient department in Rawalpindi was carried out in

conjunction with a systematic evaluation of the literature. Data were examined across various age groups to discern evolving views on safety and autonomy. The findings revealed that almost half of the participants fell within the 30-39 age range, with perceptions of safety differing markedly by age; 75% of younger women (20-29 years) considered C-sections to be unsafe, whereas acceptance rose among women aged over 40. Importantly, 78% of participants indicated that their physician was the main factor influencing their choice of delivery method, while merely 14% of decisions were made independently. Although 42% of women chose C-sections solely when medically necessary, previous birth experiences affected the decision for 25% of the group. These results imply that within the population studied, trends regarding C-sections are largely guided by physicians rather than maternal elective choices. Therefore, public health initiatives should prioritize clinical audits at the provider level and improve maternal education to ensure that delivery practices are consistent with medical requirements.

INTRODUCTION

Background

C-section, also known as caesarean or cesarean delivery, is a type of surgical procedure where babies are delivered through an incision made in the mother's abdomen instead of delivering through the vagina. It is usually done when normal delivery is not possible. It is becoming one of the most common surgical procedures done all over the world. The graph of c-section is on the rise since the 1990s, and there are forecasts until 2030[1]. There are many trends that are being witnessed that are adding to the rise of C-section. The trend is that the mothers are not able to handle the pain associated with normal delivery, which is being witnessed as is being reported back by almost all the researches. Then there is the fear of the known pain associated with vaginal delivery, and it gives a little bit of anxiety that is especially true for new mothers who are going to have their babies for the first time.

Literature Review

The trend of caesarean delivery is on the rise, as reported by WHO on global trend on C-section there is an increase of 10-15% at population levels [2]. Similarly, in Rawalpindi, Pakistan, a study was conducted there were 5667 deliveries of which 2255 were of C-section were studied, the proportion of women undergoing C-section monotonically increased with age at first marriage from 18.9% in the 15-19 years' age group to 39.2% in the 31-35 years' age group, and then decreased again for those > 36 years [3]. According to survey done by WHO there a rise in C-section deliveries were observed, with Eastern Asia having the prediction of 63%, followed by Latin America and Caribbeans (53%), Western Asia (50%), and Australia and New Zealand (45%) [4]. In Thailand, it was observed that CSR was significant increased from 23.2% in 2009 to 32.5% in 2017 and by the same rate it was predicted that by 2030 there would be rise of about 59.1% [5]. It was also observed in the same study that the rate of C-section delivery in private hospitals was higher than that of public hospitals [6]. In 2016, a study was carried out in Shiraz, Iran, in which 3940 pregnant women

took part, it was observed that 2009 women (50.8%) chose C-section, 1849 (46.9%) women chose Vaginal delivery, and 68 (1.7%) women chose water birth. In the same study, it was also found out that. The prevalence of elective C-section was considerably higher in urban dwellers and women with higher educational levels ($P < 0.001$) [7]. There were many determinants that influenced women's preference for C-section as mentioned in a study that was done in Karnataka, India, include maternal age, increased education and exposure to private healthcare, where C-sections were much higher than in public hospitals [8]. Similar findings were observed in another study done in India with important variables such as age, education of women, household wealth, and number of antenatal visits, which were positively associated, and women's parity, which was negatively associated [9]. A study was done by Salma Malik et al concluded that a comprehensive search of observational and cohort studies published between 2000 and 2024 identified 13 relevant studies for analysis. The results show that there is a large gap in the use of CS: high-income countries, especially in Europe and North America, have much higher rates than LMICs, where the lack of resources and surgical capacity limits access, and in addition, private hospitals have much higher CS rates than public hospitals, indicating that financial gain and patient choice may play a role in overuse in some settings [10]. In Pakistan, a study was carried out by Jadoon et al saw that the high rate of CS (44%) in the study population is influenced not only by physiological and medical factors but also by demographic factors such as education, income, and mode of delivery [11]. In a study carried out in Bangladesh, Nepal, and Pakistan showed that there was a sharp rise in the number of C-section deliveries in all the above-mentioned countries, in 2004, there were only 3.5% c-section delivery, but in 2017, it rose to 32.8% in Bangladesh. In Nepal, the delivery through c-section was 0.8% from 2001 to 11% in 2016. In Pakistan, it was found that c-section deliveries were 2.7% in the 1990's to 22.3% in 2017, and the result of variables showed again that they are the same for all 3 regions, which included mother's age, place of residence, education, partner's education, wealth status, birth order, number of antenatal care visits, and body mass index [12]. Occasionally, mothers deliberately use C-section, as reported in a study carried out by Muneeb Hassan et al in the South

Punjab region of Pakistan, where it was revealed that age, education, and residential status influenced the mothers' output on the method of delivery. In a study carried out by Elnakib et al in 2019, it was indicated that interviews with obstetricians provided a strong response towards the non-medical reasons for the rise in C-section deliveries [14]. In a study carried out by Amyx et al in Europe, where 28 countries participated, a different result was obtained, and the trend showed CS rate from 16.0% in 2015 to 55.9% in 2019, 16.0% to 52.9%, and the trend ranged from -3.7% to +4.7%, with a reduced rate in 9 countries, stable rates in 7 countries, and an increased rate in 12 countries [15].

PROBLEM STATEMENT

In Pakistan, cesarean delivery rates have surged from very low levels in the 1990s to over a 20% according to recent national data, with some hospital-based studies reporting rates above 40%. Socio-demographic factors linked to higher CS likelihood include advanced maternal age, higher education, urban living, greater household wealth and lower parity.

Despite increasing research, there is still a lack of comprehensive, population-based analyses that studies the perceptions, beliefs and the influencing determinants of women opting for C-section. A systematic public health study is essential to examine the trends and determinants of caesarean section deliveries in Pakistan. Such research would provide critical insight to guide equitable, rational and policy-informed maternal healthcare strategies.

Therefore, the core problem addressed by this research is:

To investigate the rising trend of cesarean section deliveries and identify determinants, perceptions and knowledge of women regarding C-section.

Understanding these determinants is essential to inform evidence-based policies and interventions aimed at optimizing C-section use, preventing unnecessary surgical deliveries, and improving maternal and neonatal health outcomes.

OBJECTIVES

General Objective:

To assess the trend of Cesarean section (C-section) deliveries and identify the beliefs, perceptions and knowledge of women in relation to C-section.

Specific Objectives:

1. To determine the current proportion of C-section deliveries in the study population.
2. To examine the association between maternal age and the likelihood of undergoing C-section.
3. To explore knowledge regarding C-sections, its complications, risks and women preference of having a C-section or normal delivery.
4. To explore the influence of persons that shape her decision for the type of delivery a woman wants.

METHODOLOGY:

Study Design:

This study was conducted as a structured literature review to explore trends in cesarean section (C-section) and the associated maternal, fetal, socioeconomic, and non-medical risk factors. The review aimed to systematically summarize, compare, and critically analyze research published over the last decade (2015–2025), with particular emphasis on Pakistan and global trends.

Search Strategy:

Databases:

A comprehensive literature search was conducted using the following electronic databases including **Google Scholar** and **PubMed**. These databases were selected to ensure access to peer-reviewed international and regional research articles.

Keywords:

The following keywords were used individually and in combination:

- Cesarean Section
- Cesarean Section Rate
- Maternal Age
- Socioeconomic Determinants
- Private Healthcare
- Non-Medical Indications
- Elective Cesarean
- Pakistan
- Global Trends
- Medical Indications

Boolean operators (AND, OR) were applied to refine the search strategy. Examples include:

- “Cesarean section AND socioeconomic determinants”
- “C-section trends AND Pakistan”
- “Elective cesarean OR non-medical indications”
- “Cesarean delivery AND maternal age”

This strategy ensured comprehensive identification of relevant literature.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:**Inclusion Criteria:**

- Peer-reviewed original research articles
- Observational, cross-sectional, cohort, and analytical studies
- Studies focusing on cesarean section rates and/or associated maternal and fetal risk factors
- Research involving married pregnant women

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- Articles reporting trends, determinants, risk factors, or outcomes
 - Studies conducted in Pakistan, South Asia, or globally for comparison
 - English-language publications (2015–2025)

Exclusion Criteria:

- Editorials, opinion articles, conference abstracts, commentaries, and blogs
- Non-peer-reviewed publications
- Studies published before 2015
- Articles not directly related to cesarean section trends or associated risk factors
- Non-English publications

Study Selection Process:

The initial database search yielded a substantial number of articles. After removing duplicate records, titles and abstracts were screened for relevance according to the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Full-text articles were then assessed for eligibility. After detailed evaluation, a total of 15 peer-reviewed research articles were selected and included in the final review.

The study selection process followed a structured approach similar to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines to ensure transparency, clarity, and reproducibility.

Data Extraction:

Data from the selected studies were systematically extracted using a structured framework to ensure consistency and comparability. The following information was collected:

- Author(s) and year of publication
- Country or region of study
- Study design (cross-sectional, observational, cohort, analytical)

- Sample size and participant characteristics
- Reported cesarean section rates and trends
- Maternal risk factors (age, parity, previous cesarean, medical conditions)
- Fetal risk factors (birth weight, gestational complications, fetal distress)
- Socioeconomic determinants (education level, income, wealth index, urban versus rural residence, type of healthcare facility)
- Non-medical determinants (maternal request, physician preference, financial incentives, fear of labor pain, planned delivery date)

This structured extraction process enabled systematic comparison of local, regional, and international findings and supported analytical interpretation of determinants contributing to rising cesarean section rates.

RESULTS

The study was conducted on women coming to OPD at Railway hospital, Rawalpindi. All of them were categorized into age groups 20-29 years, 30-39 years and 40+ years. At the end of data collection,

AGE GROUP	PERCENTAGE OF WOMEN
20-29 years	44%
30-39 years	47%
40+	8%

Perception of women regarding safety of C-section

The data revealed that 12.5% of women (all of them had education atleast upto secondary school) in 20-29 years age bracket deemed C-section safe, compared to 75% who considered it unsafe while 12.5% women remained neutral and depended on doctor's recommendation.

The numbers increased for 30-39 years age bracket where 35% of women considered it safe , 59% unsafe and 6% remained neutral.

In comparison, one third of women above 40 years considered it safe and 2/3 unsafe.

Preference for elective C-section

It was seen that in younger women (20-29 years), only 18% women preferred to have C-section, 18% relied on doctor's advice, compared to 15% who preferred C-section and 35% considered doctor's advice relatively older women (above 30+ years).

The data also showed that 42% of all the women opted for C-section only if it was medically indicated, while 25% of women chose C-section because of its previous experience.

Who influenced woman’s decision

According to our survey,

INFLUENCE OF	% OF WOMEN
Doctor	78%
Husband	8%
Self	14%

DISCUSSION

1. Local Context and Comparison with National Data

This study conducted at Rawal Hospital, Rawalpindi, highlights the socio-demographic patterns regarding cesarean section (CS). Most women were aged 20-39 years (44%) with the highest proportion in the 30–39 year group (47%). These findings align with national data showing increased CS likelihood with older maternal age, especially after 30 years [3][11][16]

Maternal Age and Perception

Our results show:

- Women aged 20–29 years: 75% considered CS unsafe
- Women aged 30–39 years: 35% considered CS safe
- Women aged 40+ years: approximately one-third considered CS safe

This shift towards acceptance with age is similar to trends reported in Rawalpindi and South Punjab, where older maternal age is associated with higher CS preference and utilization [3][13][17].

Analytically, this may be explained by:

- Increased perception of obstetric risk among older mothers
- Greater exposure to previous birth experiences
- Higher interaction with private healthcare providers

Similar patterns between maternal age and elective CS have been reported in tertiary hospitals in Karachi and Lahore [18][19].

2. Punjab vs Sindh: Intra-Provincial Comparison

Urban areas of Punjab, like Rawalpindi and Lahore, have higher CS rates compared to rural districts. Studies in South Punjab show that maternal education and urban residence as key determinants [13][20].

In Sindh, particularly Karachi's private hospitals, elective CS proportions are even higher [21][22].

In our study, we found:

- 42% chose CS only if medically indicated
- 25% chose CS based on previous birth experience
- 78% of decisions were influenced by doctors

These results indicate a provider-driven model, similar to patterns in Sindh's tertiary hospitals [22][23], while Punjab women are cautious (majority perceive CS as unsafe), doctor influence significantly shapes final decisions – a pattern common to both provinces.

3. Pakistan vs Bangladesh: Regional Comparison

Regional data show a steady rise in CS rates:

- Pakistan: 2.7% (1990s) → 22.3% (2017)
- Bangladesh: 3.5% (2004) → 32.8% (2017)

Bangladesh demonstrates a steeper increase, largely driven by private sector expansion and urbanization [12][24]. Compared to Bangladesh, Pakistani women in this study expressed stronger perceptions of CS as unsafe across age groups. However, the high doctor influence (78%) suggests potential for escalation if institutional practices shift toward defensive medicine or financial incentives. Bangladesh studies also confirm that physician recommendation is the strongest predictor of elective CS [24][25], paralleling our findings.

4. Pakistan vs International Context

Globally, CS rates are increasing, with projections of 63% in Eastern Asia and over 50% in Latin America [4]. European rates vary from 16% to 55.9% [15]. In high-income countries, women's autonomy plays a role in elective CS decisions [10][26], and factors such as fear of labor pain or scheduling convenience are prominent [6][27].

In contrast, our study reveals:

- Only 14% of decisions were self-influenced
- 8% influenced by husbands
- 78% influenced by doctors

This indicates a paternalism model rather than patient autonomy. In middle-income countries like Pakistan, rising CS trends may be driven less by maternal demand and more by institutional practices, provider preference, risk-avoidance behavior, and litigation concerns [14][28].

5. Interpretation of Preference Patterns

Our study found:

- 18% of younger women preferred CS
- 42% chose CS only if medically indicated
- 25% due to previous delivery experience

These findings contrast with Iranian and Indian studies, where elective CS demand was higher among educated urban women [7][8][9]. The relatively cautious perception in Rawalpindi may reflect:

- Cultural preference for vaginal delivery
- Fear of surgical complications
- Economic constraints

However, the strong reliance on physician recommendations indicates that CS rates could increase rapidly if provider practices change, as observed in Thailand and Brazil [5][29].

SYNTHESIS

Overall, the study suggests:

1. Maternal age moderately increases CS acceptance.
2. Most women perceive CS as unsafe.
3. Decision-making is predominantly doctor-driven.
4. Elective preference remains comparatively lower than regional counterparts.

Rawalpindi appears to be at a transitional stage – not yet experiencing the high elective-demand levels seen in Bangladesh or Latin America, but vulnerable to institutional escalation.

CONCLUSION

Most women in Rawalpindi perceive cesarean section as unsafe; however, increasing maternal age and prior delivery experience influence acceptance. Unlike high-income settings, where maternal autonomy drives elective CS, decision-making in this population is predominantly physician-led.

Comparisons with regional (Punjab vs Sindh) and international (Pakistan vs Bangladesh and global) data indicate that Pakistan remains in a moderate CS transition phase. Strong physician influence suggests potential for rapid escalation if regulatory and counseling frameworks are not strengthened. Therefore, rising CS trends in Pakistan are not solely driven by maternal demand but are significantly influenced by provider practices and systemic factors.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Based on the study findings and comparative analysis, the following interventions are recommended:

1. **Standardized Clinical Guidelines**
 - Strict adherence to WHO-recommended medical indications for CS [2][16]
2. **Mandatory Second Opinion Policy**
 - Require a second physician review for elective CS without clear medical indication, as practiced in some European countries [26].
3. **Antenatal Counseling Programs**
 - Structured sessions to educate women on:
 - Risks of unnecessary CS
 - Pain management strategies for vaginal delivery
 - Vaginal Birth After Cesarean (VBAC) options
4. **Public vs Private Sector Audit**
 - Conduct regular provincial audits (Punjab & Sindh) to compare CS rates, indications, and adherence to clinical guidelines [21][23].
5. **Doctor Communication Training**
 - Since 78% of decisions are doctor-influenced, strengthen ethical counseling training to support informed patient decision-making.
6. **National Monitoring System**

- Implement Robson classification-based monitoring across tertiary hospitals to standardize CS reporting and identify high-risk groups [30].

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